

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR ESTIMATION OF IRON IN FOLIC ACID (API) BY ATOMIC ABSORPTION SPECTROPHOTOMETER

Durga Pani Kumar Anumolu^{1*}, Kothapalli Meghana¹, Syed Sara Afreen¹, Swathi Naraparaju², Karuna Devi Barla²

^{1*}Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana-500090, India

²Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana-500090, India

***Corresponding author:** Dr Durga Panikumar Anumolu

*Associate Professor, HOD, Pharmaceutical Analysis, Gokaraju Rangaraju College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad Telangana-500090, India.

Abstract

Atomic absorption spectroscopy was used to standardize a new technique for inline quality control in the measurement of elemental iron in chemically produced folic acid. The iron calibration graph was linear up to at least 0.0148 µg/ml, which is close to the detection limit. The new method was assessed in relation to validation criteria, and the ideal conditions for elemental iron determination were identified. The outcomes showed that the process may be effectively used to estimate the elements in folic acid.

INTRODUCTION

Folic acid, as it is biochemically inactive, is converted to tetrahydro folic acid and methyl tetrahydrofolate by dihydrofolate reductase. Receptor-mediated endocytosis carries these folic acid congeners throughout cells, where they are required for purine and thymidylate nucleic acid synthesis, interconversion of amino acids, methylation of tRNA, formate generation, and maintenance of normal erythropoiesis. By using methionine synthetase to remethylate homocysteine to methionine, folic acid can regulate elevated homocysteine levels with the help of vitamin B12 as a cofactor. Folic acid can be found in vitamin B complex, dietary supplements, haematinics, and micronutrients. It comes in two forms: Folvite (100 mg ferrous ascorbate ≡ Elemental Iron-Oral) and Ferikind (100 mg Elemental Iron-Oral). Only a small number of methods reported using spectrophotometry, according to a thorough assessment of the literature.

Key words: Atomic absorption spectroscopy, haematinics

Fig1: Folic Acid

Materials and Methods

Drugs and Reagents: Folic acid was obtained as a Gift sample by a local pharmaceutical company, Iron Standard obtained from Merck Millipore, Germany, RFCL, Mumbai, provided sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, and perchloric acid, while SDFCL, Mumbai, provided sodium hydroxide.

Instrumentation

Atomic adsorption spectroscopy was carried out by using Shimadzu AA-6300 with flame atomization, slit width of 0.2 nm and lamp mode BGC-D2.

The optimum parameters for Atomizer/Gas flow rate Setup are: Fuel gas flow rate 2.2 (L/min), Support gas Flow Rate 15.0 (L/min), Flame type Air-C₂H₂, Burner Height 3 mm.

Optimal Measurement parameters are: Order 1, Zero Intercept pass, Concentration Unit mg/l, Repetition Sequence SM-M-M, Pre-spray time 3 sec, Integration Time 5 sec, Response time 1 sec.

Preparation of Stock Solution

In this study, a 100 mL volumetric flask is pipetted with 1 mL of the 1000 ppm iron standard, which is then diluted with distilled water to create a 100 ppm iron standard solution. Additional dilutions were performed in order to get the 10 ppm concentration.

Standard Solutions

Standard solutions of 0.375 ppm, 0.750 ppm were prepared from 1 ppm standard solution where as 1.125 ppm, 1.500 ppm, 1.875 ppm and 2.250 ppm were obtained from 10 ppm standard solution.

Method Validation by AAS

Linearity

The linearity was determined by Six distinct concentrations between 0.374 and 2.250 mg/l were inhaled, and each concentration was analyzed in triplicate to ascertain the linearity. Plotting standard calibration curves involved using the y-axis for absorbance and the x-axis for conc. The standard deviation was computed for the standard curve's peak area, slope, intercept, and correlation coefficient.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The relationship between the calibration curve's standard deviation (SD) and slope (S) was used to mathematically determine the limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ).

The LOD and LOQ were calculated from the following equations:

$$\text{LOD} = [3.3 \times \sigma / S]$$

$$\text{LOQ} = [10 \times \sigma / S]$$

Accuracy

The folic acid sample solution was made by triplicately adding a known quantity of contaminants at three different levels, and it was then examined using the test method's instructions. The samples were prepared according to the sample preparation, and the contaminants were spiked at 0.750 ppm, 1.500 ppm, and 2.250 ppm.

The trials and combinations used are: 50% Standard, 50% Standard+ sample, 100% Standard, 100% Standard+ sample, 150% Standard, 150% Standard+ sample.

Precision

System precision: By aspirating the solution three times, the analysis was carried out at the impurity specification level, and the percentage RSD of the impurity peak area was calculated.

Method Precision: A solution of folic acid which was spiked with impurity at specific level was prepared 6 times and analyzed as per the method for determining the method.

System Suitability: System suitability was performed by aspirating a blank followed by standard preparation of Iron 6 times.

Assay: Estimation of Iron from pharmaceutical tablet dosage form

Ten tablets were precisely weighed and ground into powder. Ten milligrams of iron were added to ten milliliters of 1M NaOH, and the mixture was sonicated for fifteen minutes. A Millipore filter paper was used to filter the mixture, and a 1M NaOH solution was used to completely remove any remaining residue. In a 10 mL volume flask, the filtrates and washings were mixed together and diluted with 1M NaOH to the appropriate level. At 248.3 nm, the absorbance of the resulting solution was measured in comparison to a blank. By filtering the response into the regression equation, the amount of iron in the pill was ascertained. Five iterations of the analysis process were conducted using the tablet formulation.

Results and Discussion

Linearity

Working standard solutions of iron with at least six distinct concentrations between 0.374 and 2.250 mg/l were analyzed to create the calibration curve; each concentration was aspirated and measured three times. Plotting

standard calibration curves involved using the y-axis for absorbance and the x-axis for concentration.

Fig2: Calibration curve

Accuracy

Recovery was within the range of $100\pm 2\%$, which indicates accuracy of methods.

Level Of Accuracy	True Vale	Amount found	% Recovery	%RSD
0	100	100.19 $\pm$ 0.0025	100.19	1.0009
50	0.750	0.7643 $\pm$ 0.0006	101.9	1.58
100	1.500	2.0749 $\pm$ 0.0017	102.4	1.71
150	2.250	3.0149 $\pm$ 0.0025	100.1	1.56

Table 1- %Recovery of Iron

Precision

When the sample was analyzed on the same day and on subsequent days, the RSD values were clearly less than 2%, indicating that the procedure was accurate enough.

Table 2- Precision data obtained from analysis

Conc. Trial	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Avg $\pm$ SD	% RSD
0.75	0.0365	0.0369	0.0362	0.0365 $\pm$ 0.0007	1.91
1.5	0.0688	0.0693	0.0695	0.0692 $\pm$ 0.0011	1.57
2.25	0.1047	0.1042	0.1042	0.1043 $\pm$ 0.0012	1.11

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The LOD and LOQ were 0.050 μ g/mL, 0.152 μ g/mL respectively.

Assay

Ferikind, 100mg Elemental Iron is used for assay and amount found was 0.19 ± 0.0025 , 1.0009.

Conclusion

The goal of the current study was to develop and validate an analytical method for measuring elemental iron in folic acid and other pharmaceutical dosage forms using atomic absorption spectroscopy. The method's linearity is demonstrated by the range of 0.374-2.250 mg/l. The commercial pills' assay revealed an iron content of 100.19 mg, falling within the range of $100 \pm 2\%$. When the sample was analyzed on the same day (n=3) and on successive days (n=3), the relative standard deviation values were less than 2%, indicating that the procedure was accurate enough.

References

1. <http://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB00158>
2. <http://www.drugs.com/dosage/folic-acid.html>
3. WHO (2001) Iron Deficiency Anaemia Assessment, prevention and control. A guide for programme manager.
4. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q3D Guideline for elemental impurities, Geneva, Switzerland, 2013.
5. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q3C (R5) Impurities: Guideline for residual solvents, Geneva, Switzerland, 2011.
6. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q3C (R5) Impurities: Guideline for residual solvents, Geneva, Switzerland, 2011.
7. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q3A (R2) Impurities in New drug substances, Geneva, Switzerland, 2006.
8. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q3B (R2) Impurities in New drug products, Geneva, Switzerland, 2006.

9. International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q9 Quality Risk Assessment, Geneva, Switzerland, 2005.
10. Armila Rajbhandari, Anjala Aryal, Sanjeev Das Rajbhandari. Determination of iron in iron tablets by spectrophotometry and atomic absorption spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical & Biological Archives*. 2013; 4(3): 435- 438.
11. Stasys Tautkus, Laura Steponeniene, Rolandas Kazlauskas. Determination of iron in natural and mineral waters by flame atomic absorption spectrometry. *Journal of Serbian Chemical Society*. 2006; 69(5): 393–402.
12. Jamaluddin Ahmed M, Uttam Kumer Roy. A simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of iron(II) aqueous solutions. *Turkish Journal of Chemistry*. 2009; 33: 709-726.
13. Anwar J, Salman M, Shafique U, Waheed-uz-Zaman Dar, Anzano A M J. Microdetermination of iron in pharmaceutical preparations by image scanning and computational quantification. *Journal of Current Medical Chemistry*. 2010; 17 (35): 4424-4426.
14. Khuhawar M Y, Pritam Das Jaipal. Spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and iron in pharmaceutical preparations using 6-methyl-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone as chromogenic agent. *Journal of Chemical Society Pakistan*, 1997; 4: 278-284.
15. Golovina AN, Levshin LV. *Chemical luminescent analysis of neorganical substances*. Moscow: Khimiya; 1978.
16. Jeffery GH, Bassett J, Mendham J, Denny RC. Vogel AI, *textbook of quantitative analysis*. 5th ed. Longman Group UK limited; 1989.
17. Ravi Shakar S. *Text book of pharmaceutical analysis*. 4 th ed. India: Rx publications; 2010. p. 271-278.
18. Skoog DA, West DM, Holler FJ, and Crouch SR, *Fundamentals of analytical chemistry*: 7th ed. Singapore: Published by thomsonasiapvt ltd. p. 547-592.